

Brij-35–Bismark Brown–DTPA system in photogalvanic cell

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Abstract : Brij-35, DTPA and Bismark Brown were used as surfactant, reductant and photosensitizer respectively in photogalvanic cell and photogalvanic effect was studied. The photopotential and photocurrent generated by this system were 786.0 mV and 115.0 μ A respectively. The observed conversion efficiency, fill factor, cell performance in dark and maximum power obtained were observed 0.5192%, 0.48, 117.0 min and 54.00 μ W, respectively.

Keywords : Photogalvanic cell, Bismark Brown, solar energy conversion.

Recently we have reported some photogalvanic cells with reasonable electrical outputs¹ but the use of Bismark Brown–Brij-35–DTPA system in photogalvanic cells for solar energy conversion and storage is still scanty and therefore, the present work was undertaken.

Results and discussion

Effect of variation of [Bismark Brown] : Photopotential and photocurrent increased with increase in dye [Bismark Brown] concentration (Table 1). The concentration of reductant and surfactant are 2.0×10^{-2} M and 6.4×10^{-5} M, respectively. Absorption of light per mole is more at lower concentration of dye and proportionately less at higher concentration. Table 1 records the variation of mV, mA and μ W with Brij-35 and DTPA concentration along with change in pH. There is optimum value in each case for maximum output of electrical properties.

It is quite interesting to observe that pH at the optimum condition for reductant has a relation with its pK_a value, i.e. the desired pH should be slightly higher than their pK_a values ($pH = pK_a + 1$ to 3).

Effect of diffusion length :

Effect of the distance between the two electrodes on the current parameters of the cell (i_{max} , i_{eq} and rate of initial generation of current) has been studied using H-shaped cells of different dimensions. Initially a sharp rise in current occurs which gradually becomes stable.

The oxidized form of the reductant is formed only in the illuminated chamber and if it is taken to be the electroactive species in dark chambers, then it must diffuse from the illuminated chamber to the dark chamber to

Table 1. Effect of variation of various parameters

Parameters	Photopotential (mV)	Photocurrent (μ A)	Power (μ W)
[Bismark Brown] $\times 10^6$ M :			
2.2	570.0	90.0	51.30
2.8	690.0	100.0	69.00
3.2	786.0	115.0	90.39
3.5	702.0	105.0	73.71
4.0	600.0	92.0	55.20
[Brij-35] $\times 10^5$ M :			
5.2	560.0	68.0	38.08
5.8	681.0	95.0	64.69
6.4	786.0	115.0	90.39
6.9	655.0	100.0	65.50
7.2	605.0	65.0	26.32
[DTPA] $\times 10^2$ M :			
1.0	490.0	89.0	43.61
1.5	700.0	108.0	75.60
2.0	786.0	115.0	90.39
2.5	681.0	105.0	71.50
3.0	450.0	82.0	36.90
[pH] :			
11.7	555.0	95.0	52.72
12.0	702.0	109.0	76.51
12.6	786.0	115.0	90.39
13.2	690.0	104.0	71.76
13.4	540.0	90.0	48.60

accept an electron from the electrode. Maximum photocurrent (i_{max}) and rate of generation of photocurrent should increase with increase in diffusion length. The value of

(i_{eq}) is also observed to be independent with respect to change in diffusion length. It may be concluded that the main electroactive species are the leuco or semi-leuco form of dye (photosensitizer) and the dye in illuminated and dark chamber respectively. The reductant and its oxidation product act only as electron carriers in the path (Table 2).

Table 2. Effect of diffusion length

[Bismark Brown] = 3.2×10^{-6} M; [DTPA] = 2.0×10^{-2} M; [Brij-35] = 6.4×10^{-5} M; light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2} ; pH = 12.6; Temp. = 303 K

Diffusion length D_L (mm)	Maximum photocurrent i_{max} (μA)	Equilibrium photocurrent i_{eq} (μA)	Rate of initial generation of current ($\mu\text{A min}^{-1}$)
35.0	132.0	117.0	14.66
40.0	135.0	117.0	15.00
45.0	140.0	115.0	15.55
50.0	144.0	114.0	16.00
55.0	150.0	113.0	16.66

Photocurrent shows linearity with intensity of light, whereas photopotential increases with light intensity in an exponential manner. Increasing light intensities increases the number of photons per unit area (incident power) striking the dye molecules around the platinum electrode and therefore, increase in the electrical output occurs. Increase in light intensity also increases the temperature of the cell and, hence in our experiment a water filter was used to cut off the thermal radiations. The results are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Effect of light intensity

[Bismark Brown] = 3.2×10^{-6} M; [DTPA] = 2.0×10^{-2} M; [Brij-35] = 6.4×10^{-5} M; Temp. = 303 K; pH = 12.6

Brij-35-DTPA-Bismark Brown system	Light intensity (mW cm^{-2})				
	3.1	5.2	10.4	15.6	26.0
Photopotential (mV)	771.0	780.0	786.0	808.0	832.0
Photocurrent (μA)	98.0	104.0	115.0	125.0	147.0
log V	2.8870	2.8920	2.8954	2.9074	2.9201

There is a linear relationship between electrical output of the cell and the temperature. On increasing temperature, the photocurrent increases but the photopotential decreases. This is due to internal resistance of the cell which decreases at higher temperature resulting in a rise in photocurrent with a fall in photopotential. The results are given in Table 4.

Table 4. Effect of temperature

[Bismark Brown] = 3.2×10^{-6} M; [DTPA] = 2.0×10^{-2} M; [Brij-35] = 6.4×10^{-5} M; light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2} ; pH = 12.6

Brij-35-DTPA-Bismark Brown system	Temp. (K)				
	298	303	308	313	318
Photopotential (mV)	835.0	786.0	755.0	710.0	674.0
Photocurrent (μA)	109.0	115.0	122.0	128.0	133.0

i-V Characteristics of the cell: The short circuit current (i_{sc}) and open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) of the cells were measured with the help of a microammeter (keeping the circuit closed) and with a digital pH meter (keeping the other circuit open), respectively. The current and potential values between these two extreme values were recorded with the help of a carbon pot (log 470 K) connected in the circuit of the microammeter, through which an external load was applied. The *i-V* characteristics of the cell containing Brij-35-DTPA-Bismark Brown system is given in Table 5.

Table 5. Current-voltage (*i-V*) characteristics of the cell

[Bismark Brown] = 3.2×10^{-6} M; [DTPA] = 2.0×10^{-2} M; [Brij-35] = 6.4×10^{-5} M; light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2} ; pH = 12.6; Temp. = 303 K

Potential (mV)	Photocurrent (μA)
970.0	0.0
965.0	5.0
958.0	10.0
920.0	20.0
895.0	30.0
845.0	40.0
770.0	50.0
735.0	60.0
712.0	70.0
675.0	80.0
	(0.48) Fill factor
480.0	90.0
350.0	100.0
210.0	110.0
0.0	115.0

A point in *i-V* curve, called power point was determined where the product of current and potential was maximum and the fill factor was calculated as 0.48 using the formula

$$\text{Fill factor } (n) = \frac{V_{pp} \times i_{pp}}{V_{oc} \times i_{sc}} \quad (1)$$

where V_{pp} and i_{pp} represent the value of potential and current at power point respectively.

Fig. 1. Variation of current parameters with diffusion length : (◆) maximum photocurrent, (■) equilibrium photocurrent, (▲) rate of initial generation of current.

The performance of the photogalvanic cell was observed by applying an external load after termination of the illumination as soon as the potential reaches a constant value. The performance was determined in terms of $t_{1/2}$, i.e. the time required in fall of the output (power) to its half at power point in dark. It was observed that the

Fig. 2. Current voltage (i-v) curve of the cell.

cell can be used in dark for 117.0 min. The conversion efficiency of the cell was determined as 0.5192% using the following formula :

Conversion efficiency

$$= \frac{V_{pp} \times i_{pp}}{10.4 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

Mechanism :

On the basis of above investigations the mechanism of the photocurrent generation in the photogalvanic cell may be proposed as follows :

Illuminated chamber :

At platinum electrode :

Dark chamber :

At counter electrode (calomel electrode) :

Here Dye, Dye^- , R and R^+ are the dye (Bismark Brown), its leuco form, reductant (DTPA) and its oxidized form, respectively.

Experimental

DTPA (Loba), Brij-35 (Loba), Bismark Brown (s.d. fine) and sodium hydroxide (s.d. fine) were used in the present work. All solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water and were kept in amber coloured containers. A mixture of solutions of dye, reductant, surfactant and sodium hydroxide was taken in an H-type glass vessel. A platinum electrode ($1.0 \times 1.0 \text{ cm}^2$) was immersed in one limb of the H-tube and a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) was immersed in the other one. The whole system was first placed in the dark till a stable potential was attained, then the limb containing the platinum electrode was exposed to a 200 W tungsten lamp (Philips). A water filter was used to cut off thermal radiation.

Photochemical bleaching of the dye was studied potentiometrically. A digital pH meter (Systronics 335) and a microammeter (INCO-65) were used to measure the potential and current generated by the system respectively. The current-voltage characteristics were studied by applying an external load with the help of a carbon pot

(variable resistance – log 470 K) connected in the circuit.

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References

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